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USE OF COMBINED SPINAL-EPIDURAL ANESTHESIA IN SIMULTANEOUS GYNECOLOGICAL OPERATIONS

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ANNOTATION

Purpose: To study the possibility of using and evaluating the effectiveness of combined spinal-epidural anesthesia in simultaneous gynecological surgeries.

Methods: 75 patients who underwent combined spinal-epidural anesthesia during simultaneous gynecological surgeries were studied. This study was conducted at the Multidisciplinary Clinic of Samarkand State Medical University, Uzbekistan, between 2020 and 2022. The CSEA was analyzed and compared with multicomponent general anesthesia. During the operation, the indices of central and peripheral hemodynamics were controlled by intraoperative monitoring: ECG, SpO₂, pulse and BP (cardiac monitor "EDAN elteV6", Germany). The reaction of the sympathoadrenal system was estimated using the urinary norepinephrine excretion rate (immunoassay method, reagent #RE59261)[7]. The response of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenocortical system was evaluated by the level of cortisol in the blood serum by enzyme immunoassay using the reagent kit "Steroid ELISA-Cortisol -01" (norm = 150-660 nmol/mol). The level of glycemia was measured by the glucose oxide method using the "Photoglucose 2/4" reagent kit (norm=3.3-6.6 mmol/L).

Results: The obtained data indicate that the application of the CSEA provides a reliable autonomic block, anti-stress protection, and preservation of compensatory-adaptive hemodynamic reactivity. The study of changes in hemodynamic indices revealed that at the beginning of the operation in the patients in the main group, the stroke volume (SV) significantly increased by 15% against the background of the decrease in the total peripheral vascular resistance (TPR) by 21%, while the cardiac output (CO) did not change significantly. There were no signs of depression in external respiratory function and no significant changes in SpO₂ during the entire course of anesthesia. The absence of significant changes in norepinephrine, cortisol, and glucose levels confirms the efficacy of antinociceptive protection in CSEA, since segmental blockade is known to interrupt the development

of excitation processes in the neurons of the posterior horns of the spinal cord at the initial part of the conductive pathways.

Conclusions: The use of combined spinal-epidural anesthesia (CSEA) has a pronounced protective effect against surgical trauma and associated adverse neurohumoral, hemodynamic, and biochemical changes. Prolonged epidural analgesia effectively provides postoperative analgesia for simultaneous gynecological surgeries as well as creates conditions for the early activation of patients, preventing the development of postoperative complications.

Keywords: combined spinal-epidural anesthesia, simultaneous surgery, gynecology.

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SIMULTAN GINEKOLOGIK OPERASİYALARIDA SPINAL-EPIDURAL KOMBINIRLANGAN ANESTEZIYANI QO'LLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

Tadqiqotni maqsadi. Bir vaqtning o'zida ginekologik operatsiyalarda Kombinirlangan spinal-epidural anesteziyadan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini o'rganish va samaradorligini baholash.

Tadqiqot metodlari: Maqolada 75 nafar bemorda simultan operatsiyalarda kombinirlangan spinal-epidural anesteziyadan (KSEA) foydalanish tajribasi jamlangan. Tadqiqot 2020-2022 yillar oralig'ida Samarqand/O'zbekistondagi Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universitetining ko'p tarmoqli klinikasida o'tkazildi.

CSEA ko'p komponentli umumiy anesteziya bilan solishtirganda tahlil qilindi. Operatsiya davomida markaziy va periferik gemodinamikaning ko'rsatkichlari intraoperativ monitoring orqali kuzatildi: EKG, SpO₂, puls, qon bosimi (kardiomonitor "EDAN elteV6", Germaniya).

Tadqiqot avvalgi muolajaning samaradorligini ko'rsatdi. Olingan ma'lumotlar vegetativ blokning ishonchligini, stressga qarshi himoyani va kompensasion-adaptiv gemodinamik reaktivlikni saqlashni ko'rsatadi. Ginekologik simultan operatsiyalar paytida CSEA xavfsizligi ko'rsatilgan.

Natijalar: Olingan ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, CSEA dan foydalanish ishonchli vegetativ blokirovka, stressga qarshi himoya va kompensatsion-adaptiv gemodinamik reaktivlikni saqlashni ta'minlaydi. Gemodinamik ko'rsatkichlarning o'zgarishini o'rganish shuni ko'rsatdiki, asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarda operatsiya boshlanishida qon tomirlarining umumiy qarshiligi (OPVR) 21% ga kamayishi fonida insult hajmi (SV) 15% ga sezilarli darajada oshgan. , yurak chiqishi (MV) esa sezilarli darajada o'zgarmadi. Nafas olish funksiyasining tushkunligi belgilari va SpO₂ning sezilarli o'zgarishlari butun behushlik davomida kuzatilmadi. Norepinefrin, kortizol va glyukoza darajasida sezilarli o'zgarishlarning yo'qligi CSEA da antinosiseptiv himoya samaradorligini tasdiqlaydi. Chunki ma'lumki, segmental blokada yo'llarning boshlang'ich bo'g'inida orqa miya orqa shoxlari neyronlarida qo'zg'alish jarayonlarining rivojlanishini to'xtatadi.

Xulosa: Kombinatsiyalangan spinal-epidural anesteziyadan (CSEA) foydalanish jarrohlik travma va u bilan bog'liq salbiy neyrohumoral, gemodinamik va biokimyoviy o'zgarishlarga qarshi aniq himoya ta'siriga ega. Uzoq muddatli epidural analjeziya bir vaqtning o'zida ginekologik operatsiyalar paytida operatsiyadan keyingi og'riqni yo'qotishni samarali ta'minlaydi, shuningdek bemorlarni erta faollashtirish uchun sharoit yaratadi, bu esa operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlarning rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kombinatsiyalangan, spinal-epidural anesteziya, simultan tashrich, ginekologiya.

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ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ КОМБИНИРОВАННОЙ СПИНАЛЬНО-ЭПИДУРАЛЬНОЙ АНЕСТЕЗИИ ПРИ СИМУЛЬТАННЫХ ГИНЕКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОПЕРАЦИЯХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель исследования: Изучение возможности применения и оценка эффективности комбинированной спинально-эпидуральной анестезии при симультанных гинекологических операциях.

Методы: В исследовании были изучены 75 пациентов при симультанных гинекологических операциях, которым проводилась комбинированная спинально-эпидуральная анестезия. Исследование проводилось в многопрофильной клинике СамГМУ г. Самарканд/Узбекистан в период с 2020 по 2022 гг. Анализировали КСЭА по сравнению с многокомпонентной общей анестезией. Во время операции контролировали показатели центральной и периферической гемодинамики методом интраоперационный мониторинг: ЭКГ, SpO₂, пульс, АД (кардиомонитор "EDANelteV6", Германия). Реакцию симпатoadреналовой системы оценивали по скорости экскреции норадреналина с мочой (иммуноферментный метод реагент №RE59261)[7]. Реакцию гипоталамо-гипофизарно-адренокортикальной системы оценивали по уровню кортизола в сыворотке крови иммуноферментным методом с применением набора реагентов «Стероид ИФА – кортизол -01» (норма = 150-660 нмоль/моль). Уровень гликемии измерялся глюкозооксиданым методом с использованием набора реагентов «Фотоглюкоза 2/4» (норма=3,3-6,6 ммоль/л).

Полученные результаты: Полученные данные свидетельствуют, что при применении КСЭА обеспечиваются надежный вегетативный блок, антистрессовая защита и сохранении компенсаторно-приспособительной гемодинамической реактивности. Изучение изменений показателей гемодинамики выявило, что к началу операции у пациенток основной группы достоверно увеличивался ударный объем (УО) на 15% на фоне снижения общего периферического сопротивления сосудов (ОПСС) на 21%, при этом минутный объем кровообращения (МОК) существенно не менялся. Признаков угнетения функции внешнего дыхания и достоверных изменений SpO₂ не отмечалось в ходе всей анестезии. Отсутствие существенных изменений уровня норадреналина, кортизола и глюкозы подтверждает эффективность антиноцицептивной защиты при КСЭА. поскольку известно, что сегментарная блокада прерывает в начальном звене проводящих путей развитие процессов возбуждения в нейронах задних рогов спинного мозга.

Выводы: Использование комбинированной спинально-эпидуральной анестезии (КСЭА) оказывает выраженное защитное влияние от операционной травмы и связанных с ней неблагоприятных нейрогуморальных, гемодинамических, биохимических изменений. Пролонгированная эпидуральная анальгезия эффективно обеспечивает послеоперационного обезболивания при симультанных гинекологических операциях, а также создается условия для ранней активации пациенток, что предупреждают развития послеоперационных осложнений.

Ключевые слова: комбинированная, спинально-эпидуральная анестезия, симультанная операция, гинекология.

Introduction. The increase of life expectancy, improvement of diagnostics, development of modern technologies of operative interventions led to the increased relevance of simultaneous surgical manipulations [2, 5, 7, 10, 15,]. The term "simultaneous" is derived from the Latin word simul - simultaneously, at the same time, together with; from the French word simultane - simultaneous, one-stage. At present, simultaneous surgeries are understood to be surgical interventions performed simultaneously on two or more organs for etiologically unrelated diseases [4,7,22]. They have certain advantages: 2-3 essentially different surgical diseases are treated simultaneously; the prevention of disease progression, surgical treatment of which was postponed to a later date; the patient's total hospital stay and subsequent treatment time are reduced; the risk of

repeated anesthesia and its complications is eliminated; the need for repeated examination and preoperative preparation is eliminated; and the cost-effectiveness of treatment is increased [17, 20]. The need for such surgical interventions is dictated by the increasing number of co-morbidities detected in women. Interest in the use of regional anesthetic techniques has increased considerably in recent years [1,6]. This is due to the current understanding of the pathophysiology of acute pain, in terms of which the adequacy of anesthesia implies the need to protect the spinal cord from nociceptive influences [8]. Anesthetic support aimed both at blockade of the afferent link of the reflex arc and prevention of additional activation of efferent impulsion mechanisms, which is achieved by including regional anesthesia as a component of anesthetic support, seems to be the optimal solution [8, 11]. The combined technique of spinal-epidural anesthesia (CSEA) combines the advantages of spinal and epidural anesthesia and compensates for their disadvantages, reducing the incidence of CNAB-related complications [1,5, 6,9].

Purpose of the study: To study the feasibility and efficacy of combined spinal-epidural anesthesia in simultaneous gynecological surgeries.

Material and methods of the study: Two groups of patients aged 40-65 years (ASA class II-III) were formed to estimate the efficacy of the proposed technique. The main group included 45 patients in whom CSEA was used as the main component of anesthetic support during the simultaneous gynecological operations. The patients' distribution was as follows: total hysterectomy and perineoplasty-28; subtotal hysterectomy and cystectomy-24; ventrofixation and perineoplasty – 15 etc. The duration of the operations ranged from 1.5 to 2.5 hours.

In the control group of patients (30) operations were performed under general anesthesia (anesthesia with the dosage of thiopental sodium, ketamine, propofol, neuroleptanalgesia (NLA), isoflurane 1.0 ± 0.4 vol%, and ventilation with a half-closed circuit air-oxygen mixture).

Premedication included sleeping pills at night and 30 min before anesthesia - atropine up to 1 mg, sibazone 10 mg, promedol 10 mg. Crystalloid and hydroxyethyl starch solutions were infused for 30 min at a 3:1 or 2:1 ratio of 10-15 ML/KG before CSEA. The choice of the puncture level (L II to LIV) was determined by the extent of the proposed surgical intervention. In the position of the patient on the side, initially, the epidural space was punctured with a special double-lumen Tuohy needle (18G) (Espocan, B. Braun, Germany), and then the subarachnoid space was punctured through its lumen with a longer spinal needle (26G). After obtaining the cerebrospinal fluid, 0.5% longocaine-heavy 10-15 mg (Ukraine) was injected. After removal of the spinal needle, the epidural space was catheterised in a cranial direction (usually 5-6 cm). As a rule, the first dose of lidocaine (60-100 mg) was injected into the epidural space 1-1.5 h after the start of operation, and then every 30-40 min. The main reference point was the level of sensory block (but not higher than ThIV), as well as pulse and BP. The level of sensory block was assessed by loss of tactile sensitivity («pin prick» test). During anesthesia there was continuous inhalation of oxygen through a face mask (up to 6 l/min). Sedation during the intraoperative period was provided by intravenous drops of Quanax (dexmedetomidine) at a dose of 0.2-0.7 mg/kg/h.

During the operation the parameters of central and peripheral hemodynamics were controlled by intraoperative monitoring: ECG, SpO₂, pulse, BP (cardiac monitor "EDAN eliteV6", Germany). The reaction of sympathoadrenal system was estimated by urinary norepinephrine excretion rate (enzyme immunoassay method, reagent №RE59261) [7]. Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenocortical system response was assessed by serum cortisol level by enzyme immunoassay using reagent kit "Steroid ELISA-Cortisol-01" (norm = 150-660 nmol/mol). Glycemic levels were measured by glucose oxidation using the reagent kit "Photoglucose 2/4" (normal=3.3-6.6 mmol/l).

The results were processed by methods of variation statistics using Student's criterion. Mathematical support for the study was performed using Microsoft Excel spreadsheet editor, Statistica for Windows and application package for statistical data processing using variation and nonparametric statistics methods.

Results and discussion.

Subarachnoid anesthesia occurred after 7.5 ± 0.3 min. In two cases there were no signs of its effective development and the operation was performed under epidural anesthesia. The reason for

the failure was presumably related to the paramedial location of the distal needle in the epidural space [1]. There were no signs of respiratory depression and no significant changes in SpO2 during the entire duration of anesthesia.

Table 1

Changes in hemodynamic parameters during gynecological simultaneous operations (M±m).

Stage of the study	Groups	Indicator				
		SV, ml/beat	CO, l/min	TPR din*s*cm	HRin 1min	BPmean, mmHg.
Before the operation	Main (n=45)	70,3±2,1	5,8±0,1	1545±151	82,0±4,1	111,2±2,1
	Control (n=30)	75,1±5,0	5,9±0,2	1430±144	78,2±2,0	105,6±3,5
Starting the operation	Main (n=45)	81,1±3,5**	6,0±0,2	1228±125***	74,0±3,1** *	92,2±2,7***
	Control (n=30)	71,8±2,8	6,1±0,3	416±1201	84,5±3,0	106,1±4,0
Before the trauma	Main (n=45)	83,1±3,7*	6,0±0,2	1145±105*	72,0±3,5*	86,0±2,7*
	Control (n=30)	77,3±4,1	5,9±0,2	1208±116*	76,9±2,1	87,2±3,0
The most traumatic stage of the operation	Main (n=45)	80,1±4,1*	5,8±0,1	1204±110*	73,2±3,7*	87,4±3,3*
	Control (n=30)	70,0±3,8	6,1±0,3	1311±142	86,6±2,6*	100,1±9,8**
End of operation	Main (n=45)	82,5±4,0*	5,8±0,2	1140±101*	70,1±2,9*	84,1±2,6*
	Control (n=30)	68,1±2,1	5,5±0,1	1401±157	80,34±4,6	96,4±3,5

Note. In Tables 1-2, *-differences are significant (p< 0.05) in comparison with the baseline values within the group, **-differences are significant (p < 0.05) in comparison with the previous value within the group.

The study of changes in hemodynamic parameters revealed (Table 1) that by the beginning of the operation the stroke volume (SV) increased significantly by 15% in the patients of the main group against the background of a 21% decrease in total peripheral vascular resistance (TPR), while the cardiac output(CO) did not change significantly. These changes can be interpreted as a compensatory-adaptive reaction of the cardiovascular system. This is confirmed by the decrease of myocardial oxygen consumption index (MOCI) and the absence of myocardial hypoxia signs at ECG control. Such hemodynamic changes in the main group were observed throughout the study, including at the traumatic stage. The blood pressure level was stabilized by infusion of solutions without vasopressors. Stability of hemodynamics was promoted by careful preoperative selection of the patients who retained the ability to develop compensatory-adaptive reactions during vasodilatation.

At the same time, a study of hemodynamic parameters in the control group revealed a significant increase in heart rate and BPmean at the traumatic stage of surgery, which was

accompanied by an increase in myocardial oxygen consumption index, whereas there were no such changes in the main group at this stage.

Table 2

Dynamics of norepinephrine excretion and cortisol concentrations in the studied groups (M±m)

Stage of the Research	Group	Norepinephrine (urine), n/mol/l	Cortisol (plasma), mmol/l
Raw data	Main (n=45)	6,1±0,9	390±34
	Control (n=30)	5,6±0,5	435±41
Traumatic stage of the operation	Main (n=45)	-	450±40
	Control (n=30)	-	677±51*
End of operation	Main (n=45)	8,1±1,1*	608±46*
	Control (n=30)	15,2±2,1**	721±60*

Assessment of the sympathoadrenal response (Table 2) showed that there were no significant changes in norepinephrine excretion rate in the main group, while there was a significant increase in norepinephrine excretion in the control group, most probably due to reflex activation of the sympathetic nervous system upon awakening.

Cortisol levels in the control group also showed a significant increase of 55% in the traumatic phase of surgery, which was not seen in the main group.

Patients operated under CSEA showed stable glucose levels during surgery. However, in patients operated under general anesthesia, there was a rise in glucose from 4.8 ± 0.4 to 6.5 ± 0.6 mmol/l during the traumatic stage (p < 0.05). The absence of significant changes in the levels of norepinephrine, cortisol and glucose confirms the effectiveness of antinociceptive protection in CSEA, since segmental blockade is known to interrupt the development of excitation processes in the neurons of the posterior horns of the spinal cord at the initial part of the conductive pathways [8]. Our results indicate that the use of CSEA as a main component of anesthesia prevents metabolic activation and associated damage to cell membranes.

The increased activity of metabolic enzymes is associated with damage to the integrity and increased permeability of hepatocyte cell membranes. At the same time in the control group patients during the most traumatic stage of surgery AST increased from 32,8±3,9 to 40,1±2,9 ME/l (p < 0,05) and ALT from 30,3±5,2 to 42,2±4,2 ME/l (p < 0,05).

Analysis of the course of anesthesia and the immediate postoperative period revealed a number of positive clinical effects of the proposed technique.

A reduction in the incidence of postoperative nausea and vomiting was noted. Thus, it occurred in 19% of patients operated on under CSEA conditions, whereas in patients operated on under GA conditions it occurred in 45%. The development of postpuncture headache syndrome was not observed; the reduced risk of such pain can be explained by the "splinting" effect of the epidural catheter, an increase in positive pressure in the epidural space due to the introduction of local anesthetic and the use of small-diameter spinal needles.

The advantages include the possibility of using an epidural anesthesia for post-operative analgesia.

Conclusions:

1. The use of combined spinal-epidural anesthesia (CSPA) has a pronounced protective effect against surgical trauma and associated adverse neurohumoral, hemodynamic, biochemical changes.
2. Careful patient selection and adherence to adequate infusion therapy using hydroxyethyl starch preparations prevent the development of marked hemodynamic changes during CSEA.
3. The use of CSEA reduces the incidence of post-puncture headache syndrome.
4. Prolonged epidural analgesia effectively provides post-operative analgesia for simultaneous gynecological operations, as well as creating conditions for early patient activation, which prevents the development of post-operative complications.

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